

Hand gesture-based automatic door security system using squeeze and excitation residual networks

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ABSTRACT

Viruses can be transmitted in various ways; one spreads through airborne droplets or the touch of multiple objects. This can occur in any area, including the entrance to the house or access to a room or deposit box. The spread of viruses that cause diseases like COVID-19 has caused many human casualties, and there is still the possibility of similar conditions appearing in the future. Several things need to be done to reduce the chances of spreading disease due to viruses, including developing contactless security support methods. This paper proposes a security system using hand gesture recognition using squeeze and excitation residual networks (SE-ResNet). This research offers a hand gesture recognition system for an automatic door system using SE-ResNet and the residual network (ResNet).

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1. INTRODUCTION

The security system for accessing a room or opening a safety box still needs to be developed along with the continued development of the expertise of criminals trying to penetrate the security system. In a condition where there is a pandemic of an infectious disease such as COVID-19, the security system for access to a public space also needs special attention. In connection with efforts to prevent the spread of contagious diseases such as COVID-19 during the pandemic and to avoid the spread of infection due to the virus, using security systems in direct contact should be avoided [1].

Some security systems use biometric methods such as voice, face, fingerprint, and finger vein [2], [3]. Several security methods require touching sensors such as fingerprints and finger veins, which may increase the chances of spreading diseases such as COVID-19 [4]. In special situations such as the COVID-19 pandemic, gesture-based systems can play a significant role because they are without touching objects [5].

Several researchers have developed artificial intelligence for classification or recognition systems [6], [7]. Pratama *et al.* [8] conducted hand code classification using the convolutional neural network (CNN) for human sign language. Then, Fong *et al.* [9] also developed security system research using hand sign recognition. The method includes analyzing intensity profiling, color histogram, and dimensionality analysis combined with neural networks as the classifier. In addition to sign language and hand pattern gesture research, CNN can predict even poor-quality fingerprint classes. This paper proposes a hand gesture-based

automatic door security system using squeeze and excitation residual networks (SE-ResNet) as the classifier in the system. The SE-ResNet performance was investigated and compared with CNN performance.

The squeeze and excitation network (SE-Net) algorithm won first place in the classification field at the imageNet large-scale visual recognition challenge (ILSVRC) [10]. While residual network (ResNet) won the most advanced performance award at ILSVRC for classification, localization, and common objects in context (COCO) detection and segmentation tasks. Combining the two algorithms is often called SE-ResNet [11]–[13]. In addition, SE-Net were used in the health sector to detect arrhythmias classes based on 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG) signals, resulting in superior classification performance [14].

The rest of this paper is described as follows. First, the research method is described in detail in section 2. Then, section 3 describes the experimental results, including the model accuracy and confusion matrix of the system using SE-ResNet and CNN. Finally, in section 4, the conclusion of this study is offered.

2. METHOD

2.1. Hand gesture-based automatic door security system

Figure 1 shows the proposed hand gesture-based automatic door security system consisting of a digital camera, preprocessing, classifier, and a mechanical system. We design the system using Python 3.0, Arduino IDE, and Tkinter [15]–[17]. The classifier will generate door security code recognition results.

Figure 1. The proposed hand gesture-based automatic door security system

2.2. Dataset

This study collects hand gesture images from five subjects using a digital camera. The dataset comprises seven hand gesture types: type 0, type 1, type 2, type 3, type 4, type 5, and empty. The dataset is acquired using a digital camera and divided into 67% as training data and 33% as test data.

2.3. Data pre-processing

Before the training process of the machine learning model, it is necessary to convert the image from red, green and blue (RGB) to binary scale. The conversion is commonly called thresholding and is the most straightforward image segmentation method, which converts the image from grayscale to binary form. A binary image is an image that has only two colors, namely black and white. This conversion stage needs to be done because it provides several advantages in the data training process on the model. The binary thresholding technique converts the background image into white and the hand object into black, often called skin color detection [18], [19]. In addition to the data thresholding process, constant illuminance control is performed in the environmental system. Lighting monitoring is one of the essential things in some experiments, such as the need for illumination studies and the measurement of lux in a particular environment [20], [21].

2.4. Classifier

This paper, investigated CNN and SE-ResNet as classifier of hand gesture images. SE-ResNet implements a mechanism that connects the output layer with the input from the previous layer as the input of a residual block activation function [22]. The mechanism is called skip connection, which aims in the training process to pass through many layers without changing and keeping the norm of the error gradient stable.

Meanwhile, SE-Net aims to improve the network representation performance in the inter-channel's interdependence model on convolution features. The performance mechanism of SE-Net allows the network to perform feature recalibration so the network can adaptively modify the weight of each feature map. This is useful for selectively acquiring global information and emphasizing fewer valuable features. The hyperparameters of CNN and SE-ResNet are designed in the same way. Both use optimizers, regulation, and data augmentation, differing only in early stopping because early stopping will stop adjusting the training process of each scenario model [23]–[25]. Figure 2 shows a diagram of CNN, while Figure 3 shows that of SE-ResNet.

Figure 2. A diagram of CNN [26]

Figure 3. A diagram of SE-ResNet [26]

2.5. Mechanical system

After we get a good machine learning model, the next step is to integrate it with the mechanical system of opening or closing the door. The mechanical system utilizes an Arduino microcontroller programmed using the C++ programming language, while the language used for hand gesture classification uses the Python programming language [17], [27], [28]. This paper adds a connecting library between the Python and Arduino C++ programming languages. The library connecting the C++ and Python programming languages is PyFirmata. The Firmata library implements the Firmata protocol to communicate with software on the host computer [29]–[31]. PyFirmata can connect several programming languages with the Arduino IDE language.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this research consist of two main parts: model accuracy and confusion matrix. The accuracies of the training process of CNN and SE-ResNet models are shown in Figures 4 and 5. CNN's

training and validation accuracy is 92.69% and 91.84%, respectively. SE-ResNet achieved a training accuracy of 95.35% and a validation accuracy of 95.24%. With the training process running, the accuracy of the two models tends to increase. Accuracy SE-ResNet is more stable, reaching a maximum value than CNN accuracy.

Regarding data prediction, in predicting 42 new images, SE-ResNet is better than CNN. SE-ResNet correctly predicts 100% of the test images. While CNN correctly predicts 92.86% of the test images. The results indicate that SE-ResNet performs better than CNN. Figures 6 and 7 show the confusion matrix of CNN and SE-ResNet models [32]–[34]. SE-ResNet correctly recognized 100% of the hand gestures, while CNN correctly recognized 92.86%. This indicates that SE-ResNet is more effective in detecting hand gestures. Both models use the same optimizer, learning rate, augmentation, and dropout. The purpose of the dropouts to the SE-Net block is to overcome overfitting [35], [36]. Early stops are algorithms widely used to determine the better time to stop the training process before overfitting occurs. This technique monitors the validation error and stops the training when the error starts to increase [37].

Figure 4. The accuracy of CNN [26]

Figure 5. The accuracy of SE-ResNet [26]

Figure 6. Confusion matrix of CNN [26]

Figure 7. Confusion matrix of the SE-ResNet [26]

4. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a hand gesture automatic home door security system based on SE-ResNet. Based on the experimental results, the model on the hand gesture dataset with binary-type segmentation reached a training accuracy of 95.85%, and the validation accuracy reached 95.31%. The SE-ResNet can classify 100% of the hand gesture images, while CNN correctly recognized 92.86%.

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